

**ALIENATION AS A PHILOSOPHICAL PROBLEM IN
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alienation, transformation, loneliness, existentialism, man-made civilization, personality, digital alienation, social network, virtual world, identity.

ABSTRACT

This article comprehensively analyzes from a scientific and philosophical perspective the various manifestations of the phenomenon of social alienation arising as a result of the globalization process, the philosophical problems that arise in understanding the essence of man, and the factors that serve to eliminate these problems. In the context of global cultural and technological changes, the transformations taking place in the attitude of the individual towards himself, society, and spiritual values, as well as their anthropological, existential, and sociological foundations, are identified.

One of the most complex and conceptual problems emerging within the framework of modern social reality is the phenomenon of alienation. In the context of the acceleration of globalization and informatization processes, the phenomenon of alienation is not limited only to the system of social relations, but is also deeply and systematically manifested in the structural layers of human consciousness, mechanisms of self-awareness, and processes of personal identification. Against the background of the acceleration of the pace of personality transformation in the information society, the intensification of the complex of deviant determinant factors further increases the scale and intensity of alienation processes.

In this context, various forms of alienation - from work, from the cultural and material environment, from social institutions, as well as from the ontological essence of the individual - are observed in almost all areas of human activity, having a serious negative impact on the social stability and functional integrity of society. In particular, as a result of the rapid development of digital technologies, the institutionalization of virtual forms of communication, and the increasing influence of social networks, the system of traditional social relations is being destroyed, and the process of alienation of the individual from the real social environment is noticeably accelerating.

is a need for a multi-level, interdisciplinary scientific analysis of the problem of alienation at the intersection of modern sociology, social psychology, philosophy, and cultural studies. This Within the framework of the analysis, the genesis of alienation, structural determinants, diagnostic criteria, and the development of social prevention and compensation mechanisms are of particular methodological importance. Because a deep understanding of the phenomenon of alienation serves as an important scientific and practical basis not only for

ensuring the spiritual and psychological stability of the individual, but also for ensuring the continuous and balanced development of modern society.

In the 17th century, the social contract theorists who analyzed the life of society deeply understood that state institutions have the property of exerting a counterproductive effect on the causes and conditions that created them. Although these institutions are initially formed as a result of the joint activities and social needs of people, they later become relatively independent structures and have the ability to exert a strong, and in some cases negative and destructive, influence on the life of a person and society ¹.

Within the framework of the philosophical trend of existentialism, the problem of alienation is interpreted as a fundamental condition of human existence. Representatives of this trend — S. Kierkegaard, M. Heidegger, J.-P. Sartre, A. Camus and others — consider the phenomenon of alienation not only as a socio-economic phenomenon, but also as an ontological and existential problem arising in the relationship of man with being.² In their view, the internal conflicts that arise in the processes of human freedom, choice, responsibility, and the search for the meaning of life are seen as one of the important sources of alienation.

In the existentialist approach, alienation is associated with a person's inability to perceive his own existence authentically, that is, his alienation from his "I", inner experiences and real possibilities ³. In this process, axiological factors, in particular, the crisis of values and the loss of the meaning of life, play a central role. A person is forced to independently determine the meaning of his life in conditions of weakening traditional moral and cultural values, which leads to an increase in existential anxiety, loneliness and alienation.

At the same time, existentialism also analyzes alienation from a psychological perspective. A person's confrontation with fear, anxiety, despair, and a sense of absurdity deeply affects his mental state and undermines the inner integrity of the individual. This situation is especially acute in conditions dominated by mass society, technocratic relations, and standardized social roles.

Alienation, as a complex socio-philosophical phenomenon, inextricably linked with the internal and contradictory dynamics of the process of civilizational development, constitutes one of the central aspects of the problem of human existence. It is manifested at various levels in human labor activity, the system of social relations, forms of assimilation of cultural experience, as well as in the processes of self-awareness and reflection. In this sense, alienation represents a state of disconnection between the social, cultural and institutional structures created by man and his ontological essence.

The deepening of alienation processes is accompanied, first of all, by the destruction of traditional social ties, the fragmentation of collective spiritual integrity, and the relativization of universal human values. As a result, the individual's identification with society weakens, and the principles of social solidarity and cohesion begin to lose their significance. The disruption of cultural continuity and the crisis of the system of symbolic meanings increase the alienation of a person from the cultural environment, leading to his disconnection from his historical and spiritual roots.

¹Narsky, IS *Otchujdenie i trud: Po stranitsam proizvedenii K. Marksa / IS Narsky - M.: Misl, 1983. - 144 p.*

²Baeva LV *Axiological analysis of the phenomenon // Filosofiya i obshchestvo. 2003. No. 3. S.*

³Heidegger M. *Being and Time* . — Oxford: Blackwell, 1962.

In the context of globalization, the acceleration of social processes, the sharp increase in the flow of information, and the dominance of the technological environment are further intensifying the processes of alienation. Transnational economic relations, mass culture, and standardized consumer values weaken the individual and national identity of a person. As a result, the individual becomes distant from his cultural roots and historical memory, and begins to appear as a passive element of the global system.

In the era of globalization, alienation is manifested not only in the material or economic sphere, but also on the spiritual and existential level. The erosion of traditional values and moral norms, the dominance of mass culture, intensifies the feeling of meaninglessness, apathy and existential emptiness in a person. The superficial nature of social relations leads to a decline in interpersonal trust and a weakening of social cohesion.

From a philosophical point of view, alienation in the era of globalization is considered as an ontological problem of human existence. As a person becomes more and more dependent on technological and institutional systems, his subjectivity and freedom are limited. This situation changes the way of human existence, turning him into an object that has lost control over its own activities. Therefore, alienation is an important philosophical category that expresses the internal contradictions of modern civilization.

In the era of globalization, mitigating the problem of alienation requires restoring human values, developing spiritual culture, and directing social relations to human interests. It is important to support human creative potential and freedom in the activities of educational, cultural, and social institutions.

In conclusion, philosophical analysis should not be limited to criticizing alienation, but should serve to develop conceptual foundations for its elimination..

References:

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